

Assessment of early childhood diet quality and the development of tailored tools for implementing dietary guidelines

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the strategy for managing, storing and sharing data generated within the 1.1.1.9 Research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/211 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research" – Assessment of early childhood diet quality and the development of tailored tools for implementing dietary guidelines (ENG)/Agrīnās bērnības uztura kvalitātes novērtējums un pielāgotu rīku izstrāde uztura vadlīniju ieviešanai (LV). The plan outlines procedures for data collection, storage, documentation, sharing, and long-term preservation to ensure data quality, security, and compliance with ethical standards and the FAIR principles.

This non-economic industrial research project aims to assess the diet quality among infants and young children in Latvia to develop tailored tools for implementing dietary guidelines. Project tasks will be divided into the following Work Packages (WP):

1) WP1 will focus on diet quality assessment of early childhood, including:

- evaluation of iodine status among infants (6–12 months) using urine samples alongside dietary data;
- assessment of infant and young child (0–23 months) feeding practices using World Health Organization (WHO) indicators and other dietary guidelines.

2) WP2 will focus on the investigation of commercial foods, and beverages intended for infants (0–12 months) and young children (1–3 years), including:

- evaluation, using the Nutrient and Promotion Profile Model, created by the WHO's Collaborating Centre in Nutritional Epidemiology at the University of Leeds;
- evaluation in accordance with the recommendations of the WHO, the International Code of Marketing of Breastmilk Substitutes, etc. guidelines.

3) During WP3, tailored tools to implement dietary guidelines in early childhood will be developed, including the creation of resources for lactating women on healthy nutrition and human milk composition, complementary feeding guidelines, and a prototype of a freely available online nutrition database.

4) WP4 will cover the dissemination of findings and communication with stakeholders.

The DMP specifies that all data collected are processed in accordance with applicable legislation, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and relevant national laws of the Republic of Latvia, as well, ethical guidelines. The plan describes the data collection methods used, storage solutions, and access rights.

At the end of the project, the dataset will be archived in accordance with FAIR principles and deposited in the DataverseLV research data repository, thereby promoting transparency, reproducibility of research, and adherence to Open Science principles.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/211

Grant

Researchers

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(orcid:0000-0003-4495-4845)

Organizations

Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Assessment of early childhood diet quality and the development of tailored tools for implementing dietary guidelines](#)

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Organizations:

[Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/211

Project: 1.1.1.9 Research application No 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/211 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research" "Assessment of early childhood diet quality and the development of tailored tools for implementing dietary guidelines"

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-03-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

An evaluation of the nutritional and promotional profile of commercial foods for infants and toddlers in Latvia

This datasets contains data regarding compliance of commercial foods for infants and toddlers within the criteria of Nutrient and Promotion Profile Model (NPPM), created by the WHO's Collaborating Centre in Nutritional Epidemiology at the University of Leeds. Available at: <https://babyfoodnppm.org>.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data is collected to assess the appropriateness of commercial baby foods available in Latvia using the Nutrient and Promotion Profile Model, created by the WHO's Collaborating Centre in Nutritional Epidemiology at the University of Leeds.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Commercial baby food evaluation using NPPM have been done in other countries, but the product availability differ from what is available in Latvia. The nutritional value and composition may also be different within one brand based on the country and legislation requirements.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

This dataset may be useful to nutrition policy makers, WHO office in Latvia, scientists, young parents, baby food manufacturers, healthcare professionals (dietitians, pediatricians etc.)

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Naming conventions

<https://www.smu.edu/brand-web-guidelines/seo-and-accessibility/best-practices/naming-conventions>

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The embargo period will apply until a scientific publication containing data from the dataset is approved for publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

The DataverseLV repository serves as a secure digital environment for the long-term preservation of research data, as well as making the data accessible to other researchers and the wider public. The use of DataverseLV strengthen the development of open science culture in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software tool that can open CSV, TXT, PDF files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Any software tool that can open CSV, TXT, PDF files.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

Datasets shall not be used for or in conjunction with the promotion of a commercial enterprise and/or its product(s) or service(s), and/or in any way that suggests that authors endorses any specific company, products or services. Furthermore, datasets can not be used in a manner that falsifies or misrepresents their content.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes, but only for non-commercial use

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-08-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The period is not specified.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The European Regional Development Fund, state budget funding, other funding resources (Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies)

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Līva Aumeistere (orcid: [0000-0002-0949-4532](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0949-4532))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Electronic file stored on a cloud service with access only to certain researchers involved in the project

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Assessment of infant and young child (0–23 months) feeding practices in Latvia using WHO indicators

This datasets contains data regarding infant and young child (0–23 months) feeding practices in Latvia, evaluated using WHO indicators. The indicators are following:

1. Breastfeeding indicators (exclusive breastfeeding, mixed feeding, etc.)
2. Complementary feeding indicators (introduction time, minimum diet diversity, etc.)
3. Other indicators (bottle feeding, etc.)

Methodology used for the evaluation are described in "Indicators for assessing infant and young child feeding practices: definitions and measurement methods. Geneva: World Health Organization and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), 2021". Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240018389>

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data is collected to evaluate infant and young child (0–23 months) feeding practices in Latvia using WHO indicators and reveal potential nutrient deficiency risks.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

To our knowledge, there is no existing data regarding assessment of infant and young child (0–23 months) feeding practices in Latvia using WHO indicators.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

This dataset may be useful to nutrition policy makers, WHO office in Latvia, scientists, young parents, baby food manufacturers, healthcare professionals (dietitians, pediatricians etc.).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

Naming conventions

<https://www.smu.edu/brand-web-guidelines/seo-and-accessibility/best-practices/naming-conventions>

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The embargo period will apply until a scientific publication containing data from the dataset is approved for publication.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

The DataverseLV repository serves as a secure digital environment for the long-term preservation of research data, as well as making the data accessible to other researchers and the wider public. The use of DataverseLV strengthen the development of open science culture in Latvia.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software tool that can open CSV, TXT, PDF files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Any software tool that can open CSV, TXT, PDF files.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes, but only for non-commercial use.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-09-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The period is not specified.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

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Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Other

Electronic file stored on a cloud service with access only to certain researchers involved in the project

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Prior to the study, approval from the Riga Stradiņš University Ethics Committee will be received. The study will be conducted according to the guidelines laid down in the:

- Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects (World Medical Association);

- Convention for the protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on

Human Rights and Biomedicine (Council of Europe);

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of

personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

Written informed consent will be obtained from all participants before the study.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Evaluation of iodine status among infants (6–12 months) using morning urine samples

This datasets contains data regarding iodine status among infants (6–12 months) who have started complementary feeding. Urine collection, iodine status evaluation will be done according to the World Health Organization guidelines: WHO. Urinary iodine concentrations for determining iodine status deficiency in populations. Vitamin and Mineral Nutrition Information System. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2013. Available at: <https://iris.who.int/server/api/core/bitstreams/a3681638-dbee-4470-8d7b-bdfc9a33cccc/content>.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data is collected to evaluate iodine status among infants who have started complementary feeding.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

To our knowledge, there is no existing data regarding iodine status among infants in Latvia.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

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